

Speculation on Velocity Enhancement of $f(e)$ Distributions and the Maximization of Entropy

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained by considering a time reversal balance for elastic 2-body scattering. This approach assumes that: $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ together with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Taking \ln of the first equation and equating with $-1/T$ of the second yields the MB distribution $f(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. This result is equivalent to considering the \ln of the number of ways a total energy E may be distributed among N particles, i.e. $\ln\{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \}$. Maximizing subject to the relaxed constraint, $\text{Sum over } i e_i f(e_i)$, also yields the MB distribution.

We have argued in previous notes that a collision may depend not only on $f(e)$, but on a function of speed which increases with speed. In other words, a fast moving particle moves through a greater distance in Δt and has more of a chance of colliding than one would assume by its $f(e)$, we argue. This function $g(e)$ (based on speed) would be a known function (from experiment) and would not be associated with any kind of variation of $f(e)$. From a 2-body elastic collision viewpoint, it seems that one simply replaces $f(e_i)$ with $f(e_i)g(e_i)$ and obtains $fg = C \exp(-e/T)$. Eave, however, is $\text{Sum over } i e_i f(e_i)$ and so one does not have the average values as in the MB case. Furthermore, $E-TS$ is no longer the simple $-kT \ln(C(T))$ result.

Here, we consider how these results change the notion of the usual MB entropy and also speculate on Tsallis entropy as we have argued in previous notes that q is an attempt to modify the weight of e/T for e/T not $\ll 1$.

Velocity Effects on Two Body Collisions

We have argued in previous notes that velocity (speed) should affect two body collisions because the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann assumption:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{with} \quad e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1b))$$

may not strictly hold, especially for higher speeds. One may see that taking \ln of ((1b)) and equating with $-1/T$ multiplied by ((1a)) yields:

$$f(e) = C \exp(-e/T) \quad ((2))$$

As we have noted before, a fast moving particle encounters more potential reactants in a time Δt , than a slow moving one. As a result, it would be misleading to use $f(e_i)$ if e_i were a large number. One might propose a known function (through experiment):

$$g(e_i) \quad \text{such that} \quad g(e_i) \text{ increases with } e_i \quad ((3))$$

to describe the enhancement of $f(e_i)$ in a collision. We focus on two body collisions because we argue these physically create equilibrium. In such a case, one would replace $f(e_i)$ with $f(e_i)g(e_i)$ in ((1a)) to obtain:

$$f(e_i)g(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

One keep in mind, however, that now: $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave} \approx E_{total} \quad ((5)),$

but $f(e_i)$ is not $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. The next question we ask is: How does the usual MB entropy change?

Entropy

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one maximizes \ln of the number of ways of distributing a total energy E over N particles subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave} \approx E_{total}$. This suggests that any distribution set of e values carries the same weight. We have argued, however, that if a $g(e_i)$ speed related enhancement factor exists, then in terms of collisions one must consider the effective presence of a particle which is not $f(e_i)$, but rather $f(e_i)g(e_i)$. This suggests that without considering the physical effects of two body collisions, one cannot really create the notion of entropy. One cannot abstractly argue that one can treat all distributions of E_{total} in the same manner because this contradicts the extra piece of information $g(e_i)$, which is a physical result linked with two body scattering. Furthermore, $g(e_i)$ is a known function and cannot be varied.

We have shown that through two body scattering above, $f(e_i)g(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. Mathematically, this result may be obtained by:

extremizing $\ln\{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \}$ subject to $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$ if $n(e_i)$ is understood to equal $f(e_i)g(e_i)$. $((4))$

If this is the case, $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$ no longer represents $E_{ave} \approx E_{total}$. For high energy cases, $e_i f(e_i)g(e_i)$ yields an energy which could be quite a bit more than the physical energy $e_i f(e_i)$. Furthermore, the entropy in $((4))$ is no longer associated with the number of distributions of E_{total} over N particles, each carrying a weight of 1. Instead, one has created an equal distribution scenario for a nonphysical scenario using $f(e_i)g(e_i)$ in place of $f(e_i)$. This is similar to the case of the Bose-Einstein or Fermi-Dirac situations, but these still use a constraint of $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave} \approx E_{total}$. Here that is no longer the case.

Effect on the First Law of Thermodynamics

The first law of thermodynamics is: $dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((5))$ with:

$dE = d \sum_i e_i f(e_i) \quad ((6a))$. If one considers dE changing due to T changing with V held constant, then:

$dE = \sum_i e_i df(e_i) \quad ((6a))$ Now $f(e_i)g(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, but $g(e_i)$ does not change with T so:

$$dE = \sum_i e_i/g(e_i) d/dT \{ C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \} dT$$

$$S = - \sum_i n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) = - \sum_i C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) (-e_i/T) + \sum_i C(T) \ln(C)$$

and $dS = dS/dT dT$. Given that $\sum_i C \exp(-e_i/T) e_i$

is no longer E_{ave} , one no longer has the usual MB result of $-kT \ln(C) = \text{Free energy} = E-TS$.

$$\text{Instead: } E-TS = \sum_i e_i/g_i \exp(-e_i/T) C(T) - T \sum_i C \exp(-e_i/T) \{ \ln(C) - e_i/T \} \quad ((5))$$

In other words, matters are more complicated.

Relation to Tsallis Entropy and Distribution

In previous notes, we argued that the Tsallis approach was equivalent to weighting various e/T values with the same parameter q . We argued that for $e/T \ll 1$, the unnormalized Tsallis distribution:

$$\exp_q(e/T) = \{ 1 - (1-q) e/T \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \rightarrow \exp(-e/T) \text{ regardless of } q \quad ((6))$$

For the above discussions regarding $g(e_i)$ to match this result, one would require that:

$$g(e_i) \rightarrow 1 \text{ for } e/T \ll 1 \quad ((7))$$

If one considers e/T as really representing $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$, then for all particles having more or less the same e_i , $g(e_i)$ is also more or less the same and can be ignored. In other words, one assumes that $g(e_i)$ is almost 1 over a range of e_i even if $\exp(-e_i/T)$ changes over this range for $(e_i - e_{ave})/T \ll 1$.

The result $g(e_i)f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ linked with ((6)) would imply that:

$$g(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / \{ 1 - (1-q) e/T \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad ((8))$$

$g(e_i)$, however, is a physical enhancement due to speed and so if ((8)) does not yield this physical result (as determined by experiment), then the $g(e_i)$ approach would be considered different from the Tsallis one.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to replace $f(e_i)$ in Maxwell-Boltzmann two body elastic scattering with $g(e_i)f(e_i)$, where $g(e_i)$ is an enhancement factor which grows with e_i . The idea is that as speed increases, the probability for a particle to interact is not $f(e_i)$, but is enhanced to $g(e_i)f(e_i)$. In such a case, $f(e_i)g(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. We argue that mathematically one may create an entropy and maximization scheme by replacing $n(e_i) = Nf(e_i)$ by $n(e_i) = Nf(e_i)g(e_i)$, but then the constraint

Sum over i $e_i n(e_i)$ is no longer $E_{\text{ave}} \approx E_{\text{total}}$ and one does not consider equal weight distributions of E_{total} over N particles. Thus, entropy becomes somewhat more abstract. We further argue that $E-TS$ is no longer the simple free energy expression $-kT \ln(C(T))$.

Finally, we note that the $g(e_i)$ scheme matches the Tsallis one for $e/T \ll 1$ (or $(e_i - e_{\text{ave}})/T \ll 1$), but that for a full match one requires that ((8)) hold which is probably not the case, as $g(e_i)$ may be measured experimentally and is probably more complicated.